

Studies of natrolite type natural zeolite and its cation-exchanged and adsorbed derivatives with cadmium(II) and NH₃ and H₂S[†]

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These studies are based on the investigation carried out on the cation-exchange and adsorption behavior of a natrolite-type natural zeolite collected as a geological specimen as a powdered sample. Cd^{II}-natrolite was prepared with saturated aqueous cadmium(II) sulfate solution with continuous shaking at 60° for maximum interaction. A portion of this exchanged derivative was then heated over a Meker burner for several days in a nickel crucible. Both the original and the preheated Cd^{II}-zeolite samples were also interacted with gaseous H₂S and liquor ammonia to study their sorption capacity and pre-heating affects. All the derivatives and the original zeolite before and after heating were analyzed by XRD, FTIR and thermal methods.

Zeolite molecular sieves are well known materials which have found industrial applications¹. Chemical and structural modification of zeolite by a number of methods also resulted in a great variety of applications. Cation-exchanged derivatives are expected to have different catalytic active sites². The porous volume of cation-exchanged derivative can be improved by heating. Due to this sorption capacity of zeolite increases³.

In the present work a natrolite-type natural zeolite has been used to synthesise its cation-exchanged and adsorbed derivatives with Cd^{II} and adsorbates like H₂S and NH₃. The effect of heating on the new derivatives has been evaluated from thermal, XRD and FTIR studies. Cd^{II} and the adsorbed species cause environmental hazards and their control may be possible by the cation-exchange and adsorption processes with zeolites.

Results and Discussion

IR study :

Natrolite and its interacted derivatives reveal strong IR bands at 3408 and 1652 cm⁻¹ which are mainly due to the stretching and bending vibration of the water molecule present in the zeolite framework⁴. The medium intensity band at 678 cm⁻¹ is due to the symmetric T-O stretching and the band at 497 cm⁻¹ is caused by T-O bending vibrations. The most important band is observed at 1024–989 cm⁻¹, which is sensitive to Si/Al ratio. The higher frequency shift is due to increase in silica content in the residual and its interacted samples⁵. The derivatives of natrolite after heating including

interacted sample show strong intensity band at 3849 cm⁻¹ for silanol bands (Si-OH modes)⁶. It is due to the increase in intensity on heating. The weak bands at 3759–3749 cm⁻¹ in all the dealuminated samples reflect the degree of dealumination⁷.

NH₃ and H₂S interacted zeolite derivatives show bands at 1593 and 2381 cm⁻¹ due to the bending and stretching vibrations of adsorbates. Cd^{II}-ion exchanged zeolite derivative shows bands at 678 (sym. T-O stretch) and 495–462 cm⁻¹ (T-O bend). The pre-heated derivatives show the sharpening of the band in the spectra and increases in degree of order within the framework⁸.

Thermal study :

Thermal data of natrolite and its interacted derivatives show a three-step weight-loss. The fast first step weight-loss of 3.51% at 180–310° is attributed to loss of physically adsorbed water, the second slow step weight-loss of 5.18% at 310–480° for high temperature water loss and the third step weight-loss at 480–900° shows dehydroxylation. This is also confirmed from the DTA endothermic peaks at 290–470°. The pre-heated natrolite shows total weight-loss of 0.76% at 180–900°. This weight-loss is very negligible and shows absence of thermal loss further confirmed by absence of any endothermic or exothermic peaks.

The NH₃ and H₂S-interacted natrolite samples show a total weight-loss of 12.93 and 13.49 %, respectively. These weight-losses are slightly higher than the natrolite sample and show extent of desorption of adsorbates NH₃ and H₂S. The H₂S-interacted natrolite sample shows a total weight-

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loss slightly higher than NH₃-interacted natrolite sample due to greater adsorption of H₂S than that of NH₃ and higher molecular weight of H₂S. The thermal analysis studies of the natrolite group have been reported earlier⁹.

The thermal data of H₂S-interacted Cd^{II}-zeolite derivative show total weight-loss of 21.51% and this weight-loss is higher than NH₃-interacted derivative and original natrolite sample, because of the higher molecular weight of H₂S molecule and adsorption capacity improved by cation-exchange.

X-Ray study :

X-Ray diffraction data of natrolite and its interacted derivatives are shown in Table 1. X-Ray analysis helps us to study mainly the geometry of the cavities and their connecting channels. It is also used to reveal the atomic ar-

angement within the zeolite cavities and also describes the expansion in the lattice presence of aluminate tetrahedron¹⁰. Indexing of 2θ and d-spacing values clearly indicate that crystal system is orthorhombic for all the derivatives.

The pre-heated natrolite and its interacted derivatives produce loss in intensity of certain peaks and also loss of a number of peaks. There is a severe loss of crystallinity due

Table 1. XRD data

Peak no.	Sample	2θ	d-value (Å)		Rel. int. for major peak %	hkl	
			α ₁	α ₂			
1	Pure zeolite	13.485	6.5608	6.5771	100	001	
2		19.295	4.5963	4.6078	12.3	121	
3		21.465	4.1363	4.1466	8.8	221	
4		31.060	2.8769	2.8841	19.4	241	
5		41.015	2.1987	2.2042	77.1	640	
1	Residue after heating pure zeolite	6.335	13.9404	13.9751	40.2	100	
2		13.700	6.4583	6.4743	100	010	
3		41.665	2.1674	2.1728	13.4	112	
1	NH ₃ -interacted pure zeolite	13.410	6.5973	6.6137	100	120	
2		15.130	5.8509	5.8655	19.6	211	
3		18.715	4.7374	4.7492	39.7	320	
4		21.080	4.2110	4.2214	16.9	112	
5		31.330	2.8528	2.8599	17.2	203	
6		48.000	1.8938	1.8985	4.3	830	
7		53.130	1.7224	1.7267	2.8	081	
1	Residue after heating NH ₃ -interacted pure zeolite	6.185	13.400	6.6022	6.6186	20.0	001
2		40.965	2.2013	2.2068	100	003	
3		44.680	2.0265	2.0315	22.2	820	
1	H ₂ S-interacted pure zeolite	13.435	6.5851	6.6014	100	120	
2		15.140	5.8471	5.8616	7.1	211	
3		18.775	4.7224	4.7342	26.8	301	
4		21.105	4.2061	4.2165	13.9	400	
5		26.995	3.3002	3.3084	7.8	510	
6		29.915	2.9844	2.9918	3.6	241	
7		40.940	2.2026	2.2081	39.3	260	
8		51.760	1.7647	1.7691	1.0	841	
1	Residue after heating H ₂ S-interacted pure zeolite	6.465	13.6604	13.6944	46.7	010	
2		31.165	2.8675	2.8675	2.0	241	
3		38.455	2.3390	2.3448	12.7	142	
4		44.675	2.0267	2.0318	30.7	303	

Table 2. XRD data

Peak no.	Sample	2θ	d-value (Å)		Rel. int. for major peak %	hkl
			α ₁	α ₂		
1	Cd ^{II} -zeolite	5.185	17.0295	17.0718	51.7	100
2		9.705	9.1060	9.1286	31.4	001
3		13.400	6.6022	6.6186	100	120
4		40.875	2.2059	2.2114	52.5	360
5		45.700	1.9836	1.9886	4.9	171
6		49.925	1.8252	1.8297	6.2	005
7		52.160	1.7521	1.7565	23.3	181
1	Residue after heating Cd ^{II} -zeolite	5.220	16.9134	16.9574	100	100
2		18.265	4.8531	4.8652	51.2	021
3		23.955	3.7117	3.7209	24.9	131
4		24.975	3.5624	3.5712	93.9	401
5		25.605	3.4761	3.4848	58.7	040
6		37.640	2.3878	2.3937	29.3	710
7		53.190	1.7206	1.7249	9.6	570
1	NH ₃ -interacted Cd ^{II} -zeolite	9.695	9.1153	9.1380	20.5	001
2		11.675	7.5735	7.5923	67.6	011
3		13.385	6.6095	6.6260	100	120
4		20.785	4.2701	4.2807	22.1	400
5		40.885	2.2054	2.2109	46.7	204
6		44.650	2.0278	2.0328	4.5	262
7		55.460	1.6554	1.6595	2.8	381
1	Residue after heating NH ₃ -interacted Cd ^{II} -zeolite	5.220	16.9154	16.9574	100	100
2		6.30	14.0067	14.0415	52.9	010
3		13.595	6.5079	6.5241	12.9	001
4		25.545	3.4842	3.4926	28.6	040
1	H ₂ S-interacted Cd ^{II} -zeolite	5.190	17.0131	17.0554	85.7	100
2		11.695	7.5606	7.5794	100	011
3		13.410	6.5973	6.6137	34.3	022
4		20.825	4.2620	4.2726	770	400
5		26.475	3.3638	3.3722	61.2	040
6		29.225	3.0533	3.0609	58.1	520
7		44.695	2.0259	2.0309	28.0	820
8		52.080	1.7546	1.7590	14.7	215
1	Residue after heating H ₂ S-interacted Cd ^{II} -zeolite	6.625	13.3309	13.3640	14.1	010
2		19.875	4.4635	4.4746	35.9	030
3		25.585	3.4788	3.4875	74.6	411
4		26.510	3.3595	3.3678	100	002
5		43.905	2.0605	2.0656	39.3	313
6		51.910	1.7600	1.7644	23.5	921

to heating as is clear from comparison to original natrolite. This also indicates that structure of natrolite has collapsed due to strong heating.

The X-ray diffraction data of Cd^{II}-natrolite and its interacted derivatives are reproduced in Table 2. Some new lines are also observed in Cd^{II}-natrolite and its interacted derivatives which may be due to the presence of cation and adsorption of H₂S and NH₃. X-Ray diffraction data of preheated residue of Cd^{II}-natrolite and its NH₃-interacted derivative indicate that a large number of X-ray peaks are reduced due to shift of diffraction peaks to higher 2θ value.

Experimental

Naturally occurring zeolite as a geological specimen was powdered after cleaning, washing and grinding to very fine white particles. Cd^{II}-exchanged derivative of natural zeolite was prepared by treating the powdered zeolite (20 g) with saturated aqueous solution (100 ml) of cadmium sulfate and shaken for 10 days. Reactants were warmed in an electrically operated water-bath at 60° for maximum interaction. After 50 days, the solid zeolite was filtered and washed before air-drying. A white Cd^{II}-exchanged derivative was obtained. One part of this sample was continuously heated over a Meker burner for three days in a nickel crucible. A dull white derivative was obtained. Adsorbed derivatives were prepared by the procedure described in an earlier communication¹¹.

FTIR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu 8201 PC spectrophotometer. Thermal data (TGA and DTA) were recorded using a Setaram analyzer in argon atmosphere at a

heating rate of 10° min⁻¹ over a temperature range 0–900° XRD data were obtained between 2θ angles of 0 to 70° using a PW 1710 BASED X-ray diffractometer.

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